
📌 Personalized Instance-based Navigation Toward User-Specific Objects in Realistic Environments

Luca Barsellotti* Roberto Bigazzi*
Marcella Cornia Lorenzo Baraldi Rita Cucchiara
University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Italy
{firstname.lastname}@unimore.it

Project page: aimagelab.github.io/pin

Abstract

In the last years, the research interest in visual navigation towards objects in indoor environments has grown significantly. This growth can be attributed to the recent availability of large navigation datasets in photo-realistic simulated environments, like Gibson and Matterport3D. However, the navigation tasks supported by these datasets are often restricted to the objects present in the environment at acquisition time. Also, they fail to account for the realistic scenario in which the target object is a user-specific instance that can be easily confused with similar objects and may be found in multiple locations within the environment. To address these limitations, we propose a new task denominated *Personalized Instance-based Navigation* (PIN), in which an embodied agent is tasked with locating and reaching a specific personal object by distinguishing it among multiple instances of the same category. The task is accompanied by 📌 *PInNED*, a dedicated new dataset composed of photo-realistic scenes augmented with additional 3D objects. In each episode, the target object is presented to the agent using two modalities: a set of visual reference images on a neutral background and manually annotated textual descriptions. Through comprehensive evaluations and analyses, we showcase the challenges of the PIN task as well as the performance and shortcomings of currently available methods designed for object-driven navigation, considering modular and end-to-end agents.

Figure 1: We introduce the PIN task, where the agent is asked to navigate toward a personalized object instance using multimodal references and distinguish it from distractors (*i.e.*, other objects of the same category as the target or of other categories). The target object, same category distractors, and other distractors are circled, respectively, in **green**, **orange**, and **red**. The total number of available objects in the dataset is 338, corresponding to different instances of 18 object categories.

*Equal contribution.

1 Introduction

Imagine a scenario where your child wants his favorite teddy bear, and he lost it somewhere in your house. In the foreseeable future, a “smart” domestic robot could be asked to find it. In that case, the robot will start roaming through the environment searching for the teddy bear. However, a-priori knowledge of the object category and visual cues related to the surroundings are not enough to solve the task, as the teddy bear has no predetermined location in the scene, could be potentially situated in several different places, and can be confused with other stuffed toys. While the recent advances in Embodied AI have significantly fostered the development of autonomous agents that can locate predefined target object categories, a benchmark that evaluates how agents tackle the challenges of reaching personal object instances in a photo-realistic environment is absent.

Motivation. The majority of current object-driven navigation tasks in Embodied AI define their goals as a general semantic category represented through text [2, 6, 70] (e.g., “chair”, “sofa”) or as a specific target instance defined by an image or description including the surrounding context in which the object can be found [9, 19, 32, 36, 82]. Moreover, these datasets rely on objects which were present at the time of acquisition of the environment [8, 13, 20, 32, 36, 45, 61, 71, 74]. On the contrary, procedurally generated environments can freely contain additional objects and annotations [21, 23, 34, 41]. However, the appearance discrepancy between these environments and the real world or photo-realistic environments could affect the performance of the agents when deployed on robotic platforms [31]. Previous work has proposed loading additional 3D objects inside photo-realistic environments [46] to improve agent navigation performance, to allow object interaction in static environments [64], or to enable navigation towards multiple goals [70]. However, no previous work has targeted loading objects that can be moved frequently and can appear in multiple contexts since loaded 3D models are kept in their initial spawn position.

Overview of the dataset. To overcome these issues, we propose the novel task of *Personalized Instance-based Navigation* (PIN), where the agent needs to locate and reach a specific personalized target instance in the environment provided as reference images and textual descriptions, without information about the surrounding context. An overview of PIN is shown in Fig. 1. In parallel with the definition of the task, we release PinNED (Personalized Instance-based Navigation Embodied Dataset), a dedicated dataset of episodes for this setting that leverages the main advantages of both photo-realistic and procedurally generated embodied environments. In each episode, along with a unique target instance, distractors objects are placed in the scene to confound the navigation of the agent. Specifically, we built the dataset on top of the semantic annotations [74] and scenes of Habitat-Matterport3D Dataset (HM3D) [56] with the injection of additional photo-realistic 3D objects accurately selected from Objaverse-XL [22]. The objects are positioned in each environment through a procedural spawning method on predefined suitable surfaces. PinNED comprises 865.5k training episodes and 1.2k validation episodes built on top of 338 additional objects.

Finally, we adapt and test currently available navigation agents on the proposed dataset, showcasing the shortcomings of relevant approaches. In particular, we compare the performance of the two main categories of navigation agents for object-driven navigation, modular and end-to-end approaches, where we demonstrate that the versatility of modular methods leads to superior performance compared to the end-to-end counterparts; still, the task is far from being resolved. These experiments assess the difficulties posed by PIN task, highlighting the need for further research on the topic. More details and release information on the codebase for the task, accompanying dataset, and evaluation benchmark are included in the Appendix.

Contributions. To sum up, our key contributions are threefold:

- We introduce the task of Personalized Instance-based Navigation (PIN). In this task, an agent must find and navigate towards a specific object instance without using the surrounding context. To increase the difficulty and compel the agent to learn to identify the correct instance, object distractors belonging to the same or different categories of the target are also added.
- We build and release Personalized Instance-based Navigation Embodied Dataset (PinNED), a task-specific dataset for embodied navigation based on photo-realistic personalized objects from Objaverse-XL dataset injected in the environments of HM3D dataset. Overall, it comprises 338 object instances belonging to 18 different categories positioned within 145 training and 35 validation environments, for a total of approximately 866.7k navigation episodes.
- We evaluate currently available object-driven methods on the newly proposed dataset demonstrating their limitations in tackling the proposed PIN task.

2 Related Work

Object-based Embodied Datasets. In recent years, research aimed at the development of intelligent autonomous agents has acquired increasing interest with the release of simulation platforms like Habitat [53, 61, 66], AI2-THOR [34], RoboTHOR [21], and ProcTHOR [23], as well as datasets of scenes for robotic navigation like Gibson [64, 71], Matterport3D [13], and Habitat-Matterport3D (HM3D) [56]. The evaluation of the capabilities of such agents can be performed on multiple embodied tasks [3, 58, 65] mimicking different real-world requirements. PointGoal Navigation (PointNav) [2] requires the agent to reach specific relative coordinates to its starting position. In object-oriented navigation, the agent is tasked to find any instance of an object category (ObjectNav) [2, 6], multiple objects in sequence (MultiON) [70], or a specific instance of a category (ION) [41]. Other embodied navigation tasks are ImageGoal navigation (ImageNav) [19, 82] that requires the agent to reach the position where the goal image has been taken, and a more object-oriented formulation of ImageNav called Instance-Specific Image Goal Navigation (InstanceImageNav) [36] that requires to reach a precise object instance given a photo of it. Recently, the GOAT-Bench benchmark has been introduced, which requires finding sequences of target objects using multimodal references [32]. However, GOAT-Bench targets are constrained to the objects captured in the environment at acquisition time. To the best of our knowledge, PInNED is the only dataset focused on navigation toward personalized targets that uses multimodal references, injects additional objects into photorealistic environments, and requires the agent to distinguish the correct instance from distractors without relying on context.

Object-based Navigation Agents. Object-based methods for navigation agents can be divided into two categories depending on their design: modular approaches and end-to-end approaches. Modular approaches are composed of multiple components, usually a mapping module, an exploration procedure, and an object detection method. Some approaches adapted the architecture proposed by ANS [16] for object goal navigation by building semantic maps to locate the target [15, 39, 55, 81]. Following, Stubborn [44] proposed a strong baseline using a heuristic exploration method. Among end-to-end methods, Mousavian *et al.* [50] and Yang *et al.* [76] worked on improving visual representations, Mayo *et al.* [47] used spatial attention maps, and Ye *et al.* [77] used auxiliary tasks. Other related work leveraged object relation graphs [27, 28, 52]. THDA [46], instead, used 3D scans of objects from YCB dataset [11] to augment the training dataset. Recently, PIRLNav [57] used a two-stage learning strategy, Chen *et al.* [18] used a method based on recursive implicit maps, and OVRL [72, 73] exploited self-supervised visual pretraining to boost agent capabilities. Additionally, zero-shot object goal navigation has been recently explored by ZER [1], ZSON [45], and ORION [20].

Personalized Instance Recognition. In recent years, foundation models have revolutionized the Computer Vision field. CLIP [54] learned a multimodal embedding space by performing large-scale contrastive training, demonstrating impressive capabilities in zero-shot classification. DINO [12, 51] is trained with a self-supervised paradigm achieving strong semantic correspondence properties among features [4, 5, 79]. Segment Anything (SAM) [33] has been trained to predict precise class-agnostic masks given a prompt. The feature spaces learned by these models are semantically rich and can be exploited in tasks that involve the recognition of general object categories. However, adapting a model for recognizing personalized objects in images remains an open challenge. For example, SuperGlue [60] leveraged an attention-based graph neural network on the local descriptors extracted with the SuperPoint model [25] to perform image matching and has been used in Mod-IIN [35] and GOAT [14] to tackle the InstanceImageNav task. IEVE [40], instead, proposes an Exploration-Verification-Exploitation framework that combines a segmentation model and a keypoint matcher to recognize distant objects and confirm them when the agent is closer; while PerSAM [80], performed personalized segmentation allowing SAM to localize a user-provided target. In the same setting, SegIc [48] introduced a mask decoder with in-context instructions on top of the dense correspondences from DINOv2 [51], while Matcher [43] leveraged DINOv2 to extract prompts for SAM in a training-free paradigm.

3 Personalized Instance-based Navigation

In this section, we outline the Personalized Instance-based Navigation task, highlighting its key characteristics and comparing it to existing embodied tasks. Following, we detail the composition and generation process of the PInNED dataset.

Table 1: Comparison of the different object-driven datasets for embodied navigation, considering the photo-realism of scenes and targets, the availability of additional objects with variable spawn locations, the modalities of the provided references, and whether the dataset is instance-oriented.

Dataset	Photo-Realistic Scenes	Photo-Realistic Targets	Additional Objects	Visual Reference	Descriptive Reference	Variable Placement	Instance Goal
MP3D [13]	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
AI2-THOR [34]	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗
Gibson [71]	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
Robo-THOR [21]	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗
MultiON* [70]	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓	✓	✗
HM3D [56]	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
ProcTHOR	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗
ION [41]	✗	✗	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓
THDA [46]	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗
ZSON [45]	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗
InstanceImageNav [35]	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗	✓
ZIPON [20]	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗	✓
GOAT-Bench [32]	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✗	✓
PInNED (Ours)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

3.1 Task Definition

The PIN task requires the agent to navigate toward a predetermined specific object instance (e.g., “a yellow backpack with red straps”) in an unexplored environment. Each target object needs to be found in the environment, distinguishing it from multiple distractors of the same category and other objects of different categories. In this setting, the target object can be provided to the agent in two different modalities: (i) as a set of RGB images depicting the target object rendered in an isolated context on a neutral background, and (ii) as a set of textual descriptions of the object instance appearance.

At the beginning of each episode of PIN, the agent is initialized at a random pose x_0 in an unseen environment. A single target instance o^i is selected as the goal g , such that $g \in C^a \subset O$, where C^a is a set of instances belonging to the same object category and O is the set of all available objects. The goal g is placed in the environment at a position z . Additionally, n distinct instances o^j ($o^j \in C^a \wedge i \neq j$) are positioned in the environment, along with m distinct instances o^k ($o^k \in (O \setminus C^a)$). At the end of the episode, the navigation is considered successful if the agent selects the ‘stop’ action before the maximum allowed number of timesteps T , with an Euclidean distance between the position of the agent at the current timestep x_t and the target position z lower than 1 meter. The action space of the agent for the task is defined by six possible actions, where at each timestep t , the action $a_t \in \{‘stop’, ‘move ahead’, ‘turn left’, ‘turn right’, ‘tilt up’, ‘tilt down’\}$.

3.2 Comparison with Other Tasks

The proposed task locates itself among PointNav [2], ObjectNav [2, 6], ImageNav [19], and the recently defined task of InstanceImageNav [36]. PIN exhibits similarities to ObjectNav, InstanceImageNav, and the recently introduced GOAT-Bench [32] (see Sec. 2).

However, it diverges from the traditional ObjectNav task because, differently from the standard objective of finding any instance of a general object category, PIN requires locating a specific instance, such as “black and white striped trekking backpack” instead of any “backpack”. PIN leverages zero-shot properties at the instance level, as the object instances used for the training split differ from those included in the validation episodes. This requires agents to focus on the specific characteristics of the target object defined by the input references and avoid being misled by instances of the same category that are not the actual target.

Furthermore, PIN differs from InstanceImageNav and GOAT-Bench in various aspects. First, the target object is represented by a collection of images with neutral backgrounds, rather than being shown in its current spatial context. InstanceImageNav and GOAT-Bench are based on a set of general object categories that are included in the dataset of scenes and, therefore, these objects are static and frozen in the 3D model of the environment. Instead, the peculiarity of PIN is that it is created using a set of additional photo-realistic personal objects from a collection of 3D objects that can be placed and moved in different locations of the environment between different episodes. Using additional objects allows to avoid reconstruction errors and artifacts that can distort the appearance of the target.

Figure 2: Comparison of observations depicting different targets in the embodied setting of our PInNED dataset with the target objects of MultiON, InstanceImageNav, and GOAT-Bench datasets.

This unique characteristic compels the agent to discern and extract the defining features of the target object while maintaining invariance to the surrounding context in which it is situated since personal objects can be moved frequently and could be placed in multiple suitable locations.

Similarly to GOAT-Bench, PIN provides a multimodal input to the agent, including textual descriptions of the target instances alongside the images. However, GOAT-Bench ignores the presence of instances of the same category of the target in the scene, whereas this is the core challenge of PIN. Additionally, it is worth noting that while text alone can sometimes provide precise identification of the specific instance, it can also be ambiguous. Visual references, although generally clearer, are not always available in real-world scenarios. Therefore, the two modalities cover different real-world requirements and both deserve to be studied. An extensive comparison of current object-driven dataset properties is reported in Table 1, which presents the following columns:

- *Photo-Realistic Scenes*: the presence of photo-realistic scans taken from real-world environments (e.g. the scenes of HM3D are built from scans of real environments, while scenes in AI2-THOR are hand-built by professional 3D artists);
- *Photo-Realistic Targets*: the availability of photo-realistic objects that can be used as navigation targets. In PInNED we carefully selected objects with realistic appearances. Procedurally-generated datasets, instead, tend to favor customizability over realism;
- *Additional Objects*: the inclusion of target objects that were not present at the time of capture. Datasets like GOAT-Bench target objects which were already present in the acquired scene, while PInNED targets objects injected in the scene afterward;
- *Visual Reference*: providing visual target references for each navigation episode;
- *Descriptive Reference*: providing natural language descriptions as targets for each episode;
- *Variable Placement*: the possibility of having variable spawning positions for the targets within the dataset;
- *Instance Goal*: the inclusion of navigation episodes in which the goal is to reach the exact instance indicated to the agent.

Moreover, a qualitative comparison of goal objects observed in their position in the environment from different datasets is depicted in Fig. 2.

3.3 Dataset

Categories and Instances. We selected a pool of 18 object categories from the assets contained in Objaverse-XL dataset [22]: ‘backpack’, ‘bag’, ‘ball’, ‘book’, ‘camera’, ‘cellphone’, ‘eyeglasses’, ‘hat’, ‘headphones’, ‘keys’, ‘laptop’, ‘mug’, ‘shoes’, ‘teddy bear’, ‘toy’, ‘visor’, ‘wallet’, ‘watch’, for a total of 338 additional objects. Each category contains an average of 18.8 objects, with a standard deviation of 5.5. The 3D objects are selected with human supervision to ensure photo-realism and uniqueness, which are critical requirements for tackling the PIN task. Finally, the 3D models of the objects are manually rescaled to have comparable dimensions to their real-world counterparts. In this procedure, we rendered each given object in a scene from HM3D and varied the scale of the object until the result was realistic according to our judgment. Hence, each of the 338 additional objects has a manually fixed scale that is adopted when the object is injected into the navigation episodes.

Input References. The input images for each target personalized object are generated by rendering the 3D mesh of the object in an isolated setting. Specifically, the input images are not expected to match the camera specification of the navigating agent [36]. The digital camera undergoes a

Figure 3: Sample input images of personalized targets from PINED dataset. We include three instances from various object categories within the dataset.

Figure 4: Plots of the distance statistics for the splits of PINED dataset. The episodes of the training (orange) and validation splits (blue) are presented in terms of geodesic distance from the start position to the target object (left) and to all the distractors (right). All the distances are plotted in meters, and the mean value of each plot is shown on top.

30-degree yaw rotation to capture a favorable perspective of the objects. Each instance is then rotated 180 degrees in yaw to view its reverse side, followed by a 90-degree pitch rotation to observe the object from above. This procedure produces a set of three input images for each target object. An illustration of the acquired reference images is displayed in Fig. 3. Moving on to the textual references, manually annotated descriptions are produced for each target personalized object with the scope of highlighting the details that allow the agent to distinguish it from other instances of the same category. Specifically, we provide three descriptions for each personalized object in the PINED dataset. To annotate the descriptions, we provided two object instances at a time to the annotators, asking them to describe one of the two objects in such a way that it is distinguishable from the other. This procedure results in a total of 960 unique words and an average of 10.7 words per description. Additional samples of input references are included in the Appendix.

Scenes. The benchmark defined by the PIN dataset is situated in the indoor photo-realistic scenes (e.g., apartments, offices, houses) within the semantically-annotated subset [74] of Habitat-Matterport3D (HM3D) [56] which consists of 145 environments for the training split and 36 for validation set. However, one validation scene is ignored as it represents an art gallery and has no suitable spawnable surfaces. HM3D was selected due to its status as the largest publicly available dataset of semantically annotated indoor spaces with photo-realistic quality for embodied navigation.

Episode Generation. During the generation of the dataset, the bounding boxes of the surfaces in the environment are extracted using the semantic annotations of the scene. To obtain the bounding box from the texture, we extracted the point cloud 3D model of each scene and ensured that each point retained its associated annotation color. Subsequently, points were clustered by annotation color to create the bounding box associated with each piece of furniture. The spawning position of each object is selected by sampling from the positions of a curated set of suitable surface macro-categories included in the semantic annotations of HM3D. The surface categories selected for the creation of the dataset are: *armchair, bed, bench, cabinet, piano, rug, sofa, table*. These specific surfaces are chosen because of the high probability of personalized objects being positioned on top.

In each episode of the PINED dataset, a single instance of a specific category is chosen as the target object. Consequently, up to 6 instances belonging to the same category, and up to 13 objects from other categories, are added to the environment as distractors. All additional objects placed in

Figure 5: Overview of the baselines designed for the PIN task: modular agent (on the left) and end-to-end agent based on a monolithic reinforcement learning-based policy (on the right).

the environment are constrained to be on the same level/floor as the agent by selecting spawnable surfaces with a bounding box position within 0.5 meters from the starting position of the agent along the vertical axis. For each environment in the training split a set of 400 episodes is sampled for each one of the possible categories. For the generation of the validation split each target category is used twice. Finally, episodes where the target object is not reachable by an agent following the shortest path are removed from the dataset. Refer to the Appendix for more details on dataset generation.

The resulting dataset for PIN is defined by a total of 865,519 generated episodes for the training split, while the validation split contains 1,193 episodes. The geodesic distances of the target and distractors from the starting position of the agent in the episodes of PINED are shown in Fig. 4. In the figure, the distribution of the distances of targets and distractors significantly overlap, hence prior information on the target object distance is hardly exploitable.

4 Baselines

In this section, we present the set of approaches that are revisited and tested on our introduced PINED dataset. These methods are recent object-driven methods and can be grouped into two categories: (i) **modular agents** that decouple the navigation task into specialized sub-modules and (ii) **end-to-end agents** based on a monolithic policy trained using reinforcement learning. Fig. 5 shows an overview of these two approaches. We refer to the Appendix for more details on the implementation of the baselines.

4.1 Modular Agents

In recent years, modular agents gathered an increasing interest in various embodied settings. These agents tackle the high-level navigation tasks by decoupling them into a chain of specialized sub-modules, each of which handles a smaller task. Specifically, Chaplot *et al.* [15] proposed SemExp, a modular agent designed for the ObjectNav task composed of three main modules: exploration, object detection, and exploitation. The core idea is that the agent explores as much as possible the unseen environment while the detection module localizes the semantic objects in the acquired observations. Inspired by this approach, Mod-IIN [35] and CLIP on Wheels (CoW) [29] adapt the detection module to handle specific instances and open-vocabulary targets, respectively. For our modular agent baselines, we consider the same exploration and exploitation modules used in these previous works, while changing and adapting the object detection module for the PIN task.

Exploration Module. The exploration module is entitled to explore the unseen areas of the environment with the scope of encountering the target object. As in Mod-IIN and CoW, we adopt a frontier-based exploration (FBE [75]) approach. The agent builds an occupancy map of the environment during navigation, and at every time step, if the goal is not detected, the unexplored frontier on the map which is closest to the agent is selected as the current goal.

Object Detection Module. The object detection module receives the visual or textual references and the current RGB observation of the agent. Then, it is tasked with providing (i) a **matching score** that, whether it exceeds a certain matching threshold σ , determines that the goal has been recognized; and (ii) a **series of coordinates** on the observation which correspond to where the goal is located, that are used by the exploitation module to project the goal on a 2D map. We select three categories of approaches to implement this module:

- ✦ **Keypoint Matching:** In this category, the visual target references and the current RGB observation are provided to a keypoint matching method. We tested SuperGlue [60], following the approach proposed by Mod-IIN [35], and the framework introduced in IEVE [40]. In particular, SuperGlue outputs a confidence score for each matched keypoint pair. We use the sum of these confidences as the matching score and the keypoints that exceed a given confidence threshold τ as the localization coordinates. Regarding the Exploration-Verification-Exploitation framework proposed in IEVE, we adapted some components to match the different requirements of our task. Specifically, we first collected an auxiliary dataset, which includes, for each goal in the training set, 10 positive samples and one negative sample containing a distractor from the same category as the goal. We trained InternImage [69] to classify the 18 categories of our dataset using the goal images of the training set. Instead of the InternImage segmentation model, since, to the best of our knowledge, no segmentation dataset contains all our categories, we adopted the open-vocabulary segmenter GroundedSAM [59]. For the image-matching step, we exploited LightGlue [42] on the keypoints extracted with DISK [67] as in the original IEVE paper.
- ✦ **Patch-level Matching:** A Vision Transformer (ViT [26]) encoder divides an image into patches and extracts patch-level embeddings. Hence, we extract a goal embedding from each reference and compute the cosine similarity with the patch-level feature vectors of the RGB observation. If at least a patch has a similarity that exceeds the matching threshold σ , the goal is considered detected. The center coordinates of these patches are used as the goal localization result. For the visual references, we employ DINO [12], DINOv2 [51], and CLIP [54] performing a region pooling over the reference objects to obtain goal feature vectors. For the textual references, a text-aligned multimodal encoder is required. Hence, we employ CLIP and, inspired by [29], CLIP with gradient relevance [17] (CLIP-Grad). We assume the mean embedding of the set of prompt templates used in CoW applied to the target descriptions as the target feature vector.
- ✦ **Detection Model:** We consider detection models that produce output regions according to a given reference. Specifically, we consider PerSAM [80] (both in the standard and one-shot finetuned versions) and OWL [49], which localize regions according to, respectively, visual and textual references. As in CoW, we exploit the output confidence to determine whether the goal has been detected and return the central coordinates of the region as the goal localization result.

Exploitation Module. The exploitation module takes control of the navigation when the goal is recognized in the current observation. After detecting the target object at a given location, the exploitation module is triggered and computes the route to reach the target object. The goal position provided by the object detection module is projected into an occupancy map, and the Fast Marching Method [16, 62] is used to plan the path from the current position of the agent to the detected goal position. When the agent reaches the goal position, the ‘*stop*’ action is called to conclude the episode.

4.2 End-to-End Agents

In contrast to modular agents, end-to-end approaches train a neural network policy to process sensor input and predict the atomic actions needed to complete the required task. We consider two recent approaches for embodied navigation and adapt them for the Personalized Instance-based Navigation task: (i) ZSON [45], which pre-trains an ImageNav agent and evaluates downstream on ObjectNav leveraging the capabilities of CLIP multimodal embeddings; and (ii) RIM [18], which employs a Transformer-based architecture [68] that is trained using auxiliary tasks and uses a recursive implicit map that is updated during the navigation for the ObjectNav task. We finetune both approaches on PInNED dataset. Specifically, ZSON is adapted to use image references as input during its ImageNav pretraining phase. While, for RIM, we employ two finetuning strategies: conditioning the navigation on textual features extracted from the reference descriptions and conditioning on visual features extracted from the image references. The features produced using both modalities of PInNED references are extracted using CLIP.

Table 2: Navigation results on PInNED on the environments of HM3D dataset, considering the presence of distractors from the same category. **Bold** text denotes the best performance among each category of approaches.

	Backbone	Modality	Navigation Metrics					Detection Metrics			
			SR \uparrow	SPL \uparrow	CE \downarrow	D2G \downarrow	Steps	%Match \uparrow	TM \uparrow	CM \downarrow	NM \downarrow
<i>Modular Agents</i>											
CLIP [54]	ViT-B/16	Textual	3.10	1.82	9.31	7.94	503.1	62.95	20.07	22.07	57.86
CLIP-Grad [29]	ViT-B/32	Textual	4.53	2.42	6.95	7.94	465.8	77.95	4.65	7.21	84.14
OWL [29, 49]	ViT-B/32	Textual	7.29	3.36	12.66	7.90	871.7	22.97	62.60	32.88	4.52
SuperGlue [35, 60]	-	Visual	3.27	1.28	7.38	8.36	804.0	29.42	16.96	3.44	79.60
IEVE [40]	-	Visual	3.52	3.07	12.25	7.73	712.1	30.03	32.39	16.01	51.60
PerSAM [80]	ViT-B/16	Visual	2.77	1.81	6.53	8.20	362.5	81.98	1.15	10.43	88.42
PerSAM-F [80]	ViT-B/16	Visual	1.93	1.28	5.63	8.12	321.3	36.13	0.60	13.48	85.92
DINO [12]	ViT-B/16	Visual	4.02	1.71	6.88	8.28	826.0	23.89	62.73	1.36	35.91
CLIP [54]	ViT-B/16	Visual	9.64	5.39	13.33	7.79	623.5	58.51	32.53	16.35	51.12
<i>End-to-end Agents</i>											
RIM [18]	ResNet-50	Textual	7.12	6.67	10.44	8.43	409.3	-	-	-	-
RIM [18]	ResNet-50	Visual	8.80	6.80	13.41	8.48	402.1	-	-	-	-
ZSON [45]	ResNet-50	Visual	9.14	7.18	21.12	7.00	389.9	-	-	-	-

5 Experimental Evaluation

In this section, we present an experimental analysis of the selected baselines on the PIN task, discussing the set of metrics used to effectively evaluate the performances and the obtained results.

5.1 Evaluation Metrics

Traditional metrics for object-driven embodied navigation are **success rate** (SR) and **success rate weighted by path length** (SPL). SR is the ratio between the number of episodes where the agent successfully reaches the target object within a maximum distance of 1 meter and the total number of episodes, while SPL weighs the success rate with the length of the path taken by the agent. Moreover, we report the **average number of steps** taken by the agent and the **average distance from the goal** (D2G) at the end of each episode. The agent designed for tackling the PIN task should be able to distinguish whether the target object is present in the current observation while exploring the unseen environment and correctly localize it, within the timesteps budget T (set to 1,000). The main challenge is represented by distractor instances belonging to the same category as the target object. Hence, we introduce the **category error** (CE) metric, which measures the percentage of episodes in which the agent stopped within one meter from instances belonging to the same category of the goal.

In modular agents, the ability to detect the correct instance resides in having large matching scores when the target is present in the observation and small scores when the target is absent. Since in these agents it is possible to determine whether a given observation matches, we compute four additional metrics: the **percentage of episodes with at least a detected match** (%Match), the **percentage of matched observations that contain the target object** (TM), an **instance of the same category of the target** (CM), or **no relevant objects** (NM).

5.2 Experimental Results

Personalized Instance-based Navigation Experiments. In Table 2, we present the results on the PIN task. Among modular agents, DINOv2 performs best according to SR and SPL. The high values of TM, CM, and CE show that the obtained matches usually refer to the same category of the target instance. The same reasoning can be applied to OWL for the modular agents using textual references. However, OWL produces fewer matches as can be noted from the %Match metric. Models such as SuperGlue, PerSAM, and PerSAM-F, which exhibit low SR and TM, have also a corresponding high NM, demonstrating that they are not able to provide significant matching scores for distinguishing the correct instances or even the correct categories. It is noteworthy that SuperGlue struggles to match the instances of PInNED, which are represented on a neutral background, contrary to InstanceImageNav [35], where the reference image is a photo of the object

Table 3: Navigation results on PInNED on the environments of HM3D dataset, without considering the presence of distractors from the same category of the target. **Bold** text denotes the best performance among each category of approaches.

	Backbone	Modality	Navigation Metrics				Detection Metrics		
			SR \uparrow	SPL \uparrow	D2G \downarrow	Steps	%Match \uparrow	TM \uparrow	NM \downarrow
<i>Modular Agents</i>									
CLIP [54]	ViT-B/16	Textual	3.35	1.86	8.01	516.5	61.86	22.83	77.17
OWL [29, 49]	ViT-B/32	Textual	8.22	3.18	7.88	929.9	13.83	93.91	6.09
CLIP [54]	ViT-B/16	Visual	11.15	5.92	7.65	666.2	52.56	35.57	64.43
DINOv2 [51]	ViT-B/14	Visual	23.13	11.61	6.62	784.5	38.64	96.09	3.91
<i>End-to-end Agents</i>									
RIM [18]	ResNet-50	Textual	7.46	6.87	7.94	487.1	-	-	-
RIM [18]	ResNet-50	Visual	10.35	7.53	7.75	475.9	-	-	-
ZSON [45]	ResNet-50	Visual	10.39	8.00	6.91	460.1	-	-	-

in the same context in which it is located. Regarding PerSAM and PerSAM-F, the results show that the feature space of SAM [33] is not informative enough to understand whether an instance is present in an observation. IEVE shows an improvement with respect to the other image-matching modular agent, based on SuperGlue. This is motivated by the fact that IEVE, differently from other image-matching approaches, combines LightGlue with a semantic detector, allowing the agent to focus only on observations that contain objects of the target category. This behavior is confirmed by the increased numbers of target matches, category matches, and category errors.

Moreover, end-to-end agents tend to perform worse than modular agents. This can be attributed to the imitation training performed using the ground-truth trajectory to the goal. Since in the PIN task the target instances can be placed in multiple locations, it is not possible to exploit prior semantic knowledge about the estimated location of the target instance. Moreover, end-to-end agents tend to struggle in backtracking and in recovering the navigation when moving in the wrong direction. This behavior can also be noted from the path length, which for end-to-end agents is shorter than modular agents, that continue the exploration until the whole environment is observed.

Ablation on Category Distractors. In Table 3, we introduce an ablation study in which we remove the distractors belonging to the same category of the target instance. Overall, metrics for all the agents improve because the presence of these distractors represents the core challenge of the PIN task. In particular, DINOv2 improves by 8.29 with respect to the main experiments, demonstrating that it embeds strong semantic correspondence properties among the same category, but that it is not trivial to identify a threshold that clearly distinguishes specific instances. The impact of same-category distractors on end-to-end agents is minor since they are finetuned to identify the correct instance.

6 Conclusion

In this work, we presented the task of Personalized Instance-based Navigation (PIN) in which the agent is required to locate and navigate toward a specific target instance. Additionally, we release PInNED, a task-specific dataset built by injecting a set of additional photo-realistic objects in the scenes of HM3D. Finally, we perform an extensive analysis of recent navigation methods adapted for the proposed task. Experimental results demonstrate that the new challenges in the recognition of specific instances introduced in our proposed task are still far from being addressed. This benchmark sets a novel testbed for future work on embodied navigation toward personalized instances.

Acknowledgments and Disclosure of Funding

This work has been conducted under a research grant co-funded by Leonardo S.p.A. and supported by the EU Horizon project “ELIAS - European Lighthouse of AI for Sustainability” (No. 101120237), the project “Personalized Robotics as Service Oriented Applications (PERSEO)” funded under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Action Horizon 2020 (No. 955778), and the PNRR project “Fit for Medical Robotics (Fit4MedRob)” funded by the Italian Ministry of University and Research.

References

- [1] Ziad Al-Halah, Santhosh Kumar Ramakrishnan, and Kristen Grauman. Zero Experience Required: Plug & Play Modular Transfer Learning for Semantic Visual Navigation. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2022.
- [2] Peter Anderson, Angel Chang, Devendra Singh Chaplot, Alexey Dosovitskiy, Saurabh Gupta, Vladlen Koltun, Jana Kosecka, Jitendra Malik, Roozbeh Mottaghi, Manolis Savva, et al. On Evaluation of Embodied Navigation Agents. *arXiv:1807.06757*, 2018.
- [3] Peter Anderson, Qi Wu, Damien Teney, Jake Bruce, Mark Johnson, Niko Sünderhauf, Ian Reid, Stephen Gould, and Anton Van Den Hengel. Vision-and-Language Navigation: Interpreting Visually-Grounded Navigation Instructions in Real Environments. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2018.
- [4] Luca Barsellotti, Roberto Amoroso, Lorenzo Baraldi, and Rita Cucchiara. FOSSIL: Free Open-Vocabulary Semantic Segmentation Through Synthetic References Retrieval. In *Proceedings of the IEEE Winter Conference on Applications of Computer Vision*, 2024.
- [5] Luca Barsellotti, Roberto Amoroso, Marcella Cornia, Lorenzo Baraldi, and Rita Cucchiara. Training-Free Open-Vocabulary Segmentation with Offline Diffusion-Augmented Prototype Generation. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2024.
- [6] Dhruv Batra, Aaron Gokaslan, Aniruddha Kembhavi, Oleksandr Maksymets, Roozbeh Mottaghi, Manolis Savva, Alexander Toshev, and Erik Wijmans. ObjectNav Revisited: On Evaluation of Embodied Agents Navigating to Objects. *arXiv:2006.13171*, 2020.
- [7] Lorenzo Bianchi, Fabio Carrara, Nicola Messina, Claudio Gennaro, and Fabrizio Falchi. The devil is in the fine-grained details: Evaluating open-vocabulary object detectors for fine-grained understanding. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2024.
- [8] Roberto Bigazzi, Lorenzo Baraldi, Shreyas Kousik, Rita Cucchiara, and Marco Pavone. Mapping High-level Semantic Regions in Indoor Environments without Object Recognition. In *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation*, 2024.
- [9] Roberto Bigazzi, Marcella Cornia, Silvia Cascianelli, Lorenzo Baraldi, and Rita Cucchiara. Embodied Agents for Efficient Exploration and Smart Scene Description. In *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation*, 2023.
- [10] Maria A Bravo, Sudhanshu Mittal, Simon Ging, and Thomas Brox. Open-Vocabulary Attribute Detection. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2023.
- [11] Berk Calli, Arjun Singh, Aaron Walsman, Siddhartha Srinivasa, Pieter Abbeel, and Aaron M Dollar. The YCB Object and Model Set: Towards Common Benchmarks for Manipulation Research. In *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Advanced Robotics*, 2015.
- [12] Mathilde Caron, Hugo Touvron, Ishan Misra, Hervé Jégou, Julien Mairal, Piotr Bojanowski, and Armand Joulin. Emerging Properties in Self-Supervised Vision Transformers. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision*, 2021.
- [13] Angel Chang, Angela Dai, Thomas Funkhouser, Maciej Halber, Matthias Niessner, Manolis Savva, Shuran Song, Andy Zeng, and Yinda Zhang. Matterport3D: Learning from RGB-D Data in Indoor Environments. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on 3D Vision*, 2017.
- [14] Matthew Chang, Theophile Gervet, Mukul Khanna, Sriram Yenamandra, Dhruv Shah, So Yeon Min, Kavita Shah, Chris Paxton, Saurabh Gupta, Dhruv Batra, et al. GOAT: GO to Any Thing. In *Proceedings of Robotics: Science and Systems*, 2024.
- [15] Devendra Singh Chaplot, Dhiraj Prakashchand Gandhi, Abhinav Gupta, and Russ R Salakhutdinov. Object Goal Navigation using Goal-Oriented Semantic Exploration. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 2020.

- [16] Devendra Singh Chaplot, Ruslan Salakhutdinov, Abhinav Gupta, and Saurabh Gupta. Neural Topological SLAM for Visual Navigation. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2020.
- [17] Hila Chefer, Shir Gur, and Lior Wolf. Transformer Interpretability Beyond Attention Visualization. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2021.
- [18] Shizhe Chen, Thomas Chabal, Ivan Laptev, and Cordelia Schmid. Object Goal Navigation with Recursive Implicit Maps. In *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems*, 2023.
- [19] Yunho Choi and Songhwai Oh. Image-Goal Navigation via Keypoint-Based Reinforcement Learning. In *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Ubiquitous Robots*, 2021.
- [20] Yinpei Dai, Run Peng, Sikai Li, and Joyce Chai. Think, Act, and Ask: Open-World Interactive Personalized Robot Navigation. In *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation*, 2024.
- [21] Matt Deitke, Winson Han, Alvaro Herrasti, Aniruddha Kembhavi, Eric Kolve, Roozbeh Mottaghi, Jordi Salvador, Dustin Schwenk, Eli VanderBilt, Matthew Wallingford, et al. RoboTHOR: An Open Simulation-to-Real Embodied AI Platform. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2020.
- [22] Matt Deitke, Ruoshi Liu, Matthew Wallingford, Huong Ngo, Oscar Michel, Aditya Kusupati, Alan Fan, Christian Laforte, Vikram Voleti, Samir Yitzhak Gadre, et al. Objaverse-XL: A Universe of 10M+ 3D Objects. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 2023.
- [23] Matt Deitke, Eli VanderBilt, Alvaro Herrasti, Luca Weihs, Kiana Ehsani, Jordi Salvador, Winson Han, Eric Kolve, Aniruddha Kembhavi, and Roozbeh Mottaghi. ProcTHOR: Large-Scale Embodied AI Using Procedural Generation. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 2022.
- [24] Jia Deng, Wei Dong, Richard Socher, Li-Jia Li, Kai Li, and Li Fei-Fei. ImageNet: A large-scale hierarchical image database. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2009.
- [25] Daniel DeTone, Tomasz Malisiewicz, and Andrew Rabinovich. SuperPoint: Self-Supervised Interest Point Detection and Description. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Workshops*, 2018.
- [26] Alexey Dosovitskiy, Lucas Beyer, Alexander Kolesnikov, Dirk Weissenborn, Xiaohua Zhai, Thomas Unterthiner, Mostafa Dehghani, Matthias Minderer, Georg Heigold, Sylvain Gelly, Jakob Uszkoreit, and Neil Houlsby. An Image is Worth 16x16 Words: Transformers for Image Recognition at Scale. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Learning Representations*, 2021.
- [27] Raphael Druon, Yusuke Yoshiyasu, Asako Kanezaki, and Alassane Watt. Visual Object Search by Learning Spatial Context. *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*, 2020.
- [28] Heming Du, Xin Yu, and Liang Zheng. Learning Object Relation Graph and Tentative Policy for Visual Navigation. In *Proceedings of the European Conference on Computer Vision*, 2020.
- [29] Samir Yitzhak Gadre, Mitchell Wortsman, Gabriel Ilharco, Ludwig Schmidt, and Shuran Song. CoWs on Pasture: Baselines and Benchmarks for Language-Driven Zero-Shot Object Navigation. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2023.
- [30] Timnit Gebru, Jamie Morgenstern, Briana Vecchione, Jennifer Wortman Vaughan, Hanna Wallach, Hal Daumé Iii, and Kate Crawford. Datasheets for Datasets. *Communications of the ACM*, 2021.

- [31] Abhishek Kadian, Joanne Truong, Aaron Gokaslan, Alexander Clegg, Erik Wijmans, Stefan Lee, Manolis Savva, Sonia Chernova, and Dhruv Batra. Sim2Real Predictivity: Does Evaluation in Simulation Predict Real-World Performance? *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*, 2020.
- [32] Mukul Khanna, Ram Ramrakhya, Gunjan Chhablani, Sriram Yenamandra, Theophile Gervet, Matthew Chang, Zsolt Kira, Devendra Singh Chaplot, Dhruv Batra, and Roozbeh Mottaghi. GOAT-Bench: A Benchmark for Multi-Modal Lifelong Navigation. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2024.
- [33] Alexander Kirillov, Eric Mintun, Nikhila Ravi, Hanzi Mao, Chloe Rolland, Laura Gustafson, Tete Xiao, Spencer Whitehead, Alexander C. Berg, Wan-Yen Lo, Piotr Dollár, and Ross Girshick. Segment Anything. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision*, 2023.
- [34] Eric Kolve, Roozbeh Mottaghi, Winson Han, Eli VanderBilt, Luca Weihs, Alvaro Herrasti, Matt Deitke, Kiana Ehsani, Daniel Gordon, Yuke Zhu, et al. AI2-THOR: An Interactive 3D Environment for Visual AI. *arXiv:1712.05474*, 2017.
- [35] Jacob Krantz, Theophile Gervet, Karmesh Yadav, Austin Wang, Chris Paxton, Roozbeh Mottaghi, Dhruv Batra, Jitendra Malik, Stefan Lee, and Devendra Singh Chaplot. Navigating to Objects Specified by Images. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision*, 2023.
- [36] Jacob Krantz, Stefan Lee, Jitendra Malik, Dhruv Batra, and Devendra Singh Chaplot. Instance-Specific Image Goal Navigation: Training Embodied Agents to Find Object Instances. *arXiv:2211.15876*, 2022.
- [37] Ranjay Krishna, Yuke Zhu, Oliver Groth, Justin Johnson, Kenji Hata, Joshua Kravitz, Stephanie Chen, Yannis Kalantidis, Li-Jia Li, David A Shamma, et al. Visual Genome: Connecting Language and Vision Using Crowdsourced Dense Image Annotations. *International Journal of Computer Vision*, 2017.
- [38] Alina Kuznetsova, Hassan Rom, Neil Alldrin, Jasper Uijlings, Ivan Krasin, Jordi Pont-Tuset, Shahab Kamali, Stefan Popov, Matteo Mallocci, Alexander Kolesnikov, Tom Duerig, and Vittorio Ferrari. The Open Images Dataset V4. *International Journal of Computer Vision*, 2020.
- [39] Federico Landi, Roberto Bigazzi, Marcella Cornia, Silvia Cascianelli, Lorenzo Baraldi, and Rita Cucchiara. Spot the Difference: A Novel Task for Embodied Agents in Changing Environments. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Pattern Recognition*, 2022.
- [40] Xiaohan Lei, Min Wang, Wengang Zhou, Li Li, and Houqiang Li. Instance-aware Exploration-Verification-Exploitation for Instance ImageGoal Navigation. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2024.
- [41] Weijie Li, Xinhang Song, Yubing Bai, Sixian Zhang, and Shuqiang Jiang. ION: Instance-level Object Navigation. In *Proceedings of the ACM International Conference on Multimedia*, 2021.
- [42] Philipp Lindenberger, Paul-Edouard Sarlin, and Marc Pollefeys. LightGlue: Local Feature Matching at Light Speed. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision*, 2023.
- [43] Yang Liu, Muzhi Zhu, Hengtao Li, Hao Chen, Xinlong Wang, and Chunhua Shen. Matcher: Segment Anything with One Shot Using All-Purpose Feature Matching. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Learning Representations*, 2024.
- [44] Haokuan Luo, Albert Yue, Zhang-Wei Hong, and Pulkit Agrawal. Stubborn: A Strong Baseline for Indoor Object Navigation. In *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems*, 2022.
- [45] Arjun Majumdar, Gunjan Aggarwal, Bhavika Devnani, Judy Hoffman, and Dhruv Batra. ZSON: Zero-Shot Object-Goal Navigation using Multimodal Goal Embeddings. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 2022.

- [46] Oleksandr Maksymets, Vincent Cartillier, Aaron Gokaslan, Erik Wijmans, Wojciech Galuba, Stefan Lee, and Dhruv Batra. THDA: Treasure Hunt Data Augmentation for Semantic Navigation. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision*, 2021.
- [47] Bar Mayo, Tamir Hazan, and Ayellet Tal. Visual Navigation with Spatial Attention. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2021.
- [48] Lingchen Meng, Shiyi Lan, Hengduo Li, Jose M Alvarez, Zuxuan Wu, and Yu-Gang Jiang. SEGIC: Unleashing the Emergent Correspondence for In-Context Segmentation. In *Proceedings of the European Conference on Computer Vision*, 2024.
- [49] Matthias Minderer, Alexey Gritsenko, Austin Stone, Maxim Neumann, Dirk Weissenborn, Alexey Dosovitskiy, Aravindh Mahendran, Anurag Arnab, Mostafa Dehghani, Zhuoran Shen, et al. Simple Open-Vocabulary Object Detection. In *Proceedings of the European Conference on Computer Vision*, 2022.
- [50] Arsalan Mousavian, Alexander Toshev, Marek Fišer, Jana Košecká, Ayzaan Wahid, and James Davidson. Visual Representations for Semantic Target Driven Navigation. In *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation*, 2019.
- [51] Maxime Oquab, Timothée Darcet, Théo Moutakanni, Huy Vo, Marc Szafranec, Vasil Khalidov, Pierre Fernandez, Daniel Haziza, Francisco Massa, Alaaeldin El-Nouby, et al. DINOv2: Learning Robust Visual Features without Supervision. *arXiv:2304.07193*, 2023.
- [52] Anwesan Pal, Yiding Qiu, and Henrik Christensen. Learning hierarchical relationships for object-goal navigation. In *Proceedings of the Conference on Robot Learning*, 2021.
- [53] Xavier Puig, Eric Undersander, Andrew Szot, Mikael Dallaire Cote, Tsung-Yen Yang, Ruslan Partsey, Ruta Desai, Alexander William Clegg, Michal Hlavac, So Yeon Min, et al. Habitat 3.0: A Co-Habitat for Humans, Avatars and Robots. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Learning Representations*, 2024.
- [54] Alec Radford, Jong Wook Kim, Chris Hallacy, Aditya Ramesh, Gabriel Goh, Sandhini Agarwal, Girish Sastry, Amanda Askell, Pamela Mishkin, Jack Clark, Gretchen Krueger, and Ilya Sutskever. Learning Transferable Visual Models From Natural Language Supervision. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Machine Learning*, 2021.
- [55] Santhosh Kumar Ramakrishnan, Devendra Singh Chaplot, Ziad Al-Halah, Jitendra Malik, and Kristen Grauman. PONI: Potential Functions for ObjectGoal Navigation with Interaction-free Learning. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2022.
- [56] Santhosh Kumar Ramakrishnan, Aaron Gokaslan, Erik Wijmans, Oleksandr Maksymets, Alexander Clegg, John M Turner, Eric Undersander, Wojciech Galuba, Andrew Westbury, Angel X Chang, Manolis Savva, Yili Zhao, and Dhruv Batra. Habitat-Matterport 3D Dataset (HM3D): 1000 Large-scale 3D Environments for Embodied AI. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 2021.
- [57] Ram Ramrakhya, Dhruv Batra, Erik Wijmans, and Abhishek Das. PIRLNav: Pretraining With Imitation and RL Finetuning for ObjectNav. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2023.
- [58] Niyati Rawal, Roberto Bigazzi, Lorenzo Baraldi, and Rita Cucchiara. AIGeN: An Adversarial Approach for Instruction Generation in VLN. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Workshops*, 2024.
- [59] Tianhe Ren, Shilong Liu, Ailing Zeng, Jing Lin, Kunchang Li, He Cao, Jiayu Chen, Xinyu Huang, Yukang Chen, Feng Yan, et al. Grounded SAM: Assembling Open-World Models for Diverse Visual Tasks. *arXiv:2401.14159*, 2024.
- [60] Paul-Edouard Sarlin, Daniel DeTone, Tomasz Malisiewicz, and Andrew Rabinovich. SuperGlue: Learning Feature Matching With Graph Neural Networks. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2020.

- [61] Manolis Savva, Abhishek Kadian, Oleksandr Maksymets, Yili Zhao, Erik Wijmans, Bhavana Jain, Julian Straub, Jia Liu, Vladlen Koltun, Jitendra Malik, et al. Habitat: A Platform for Embodied AI Research. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2019.
- [62] James A Sethian. A Fast Marching Level Set Method for Monotonically Advancing Fronts. In *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 1996.
- [63] Shuai Shao, Zeming Li, Tianyuan Zhang, Chao Peng, Gang Yu, Xiangyu Zhang, Jing Li, and Jian Sun. Objects365: A Large-Scale, High-Quality Dataset for Object Detection. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision*, 2019.
- [64] Bokui Shen, Fei Xia, Chengshu Li, Roberto Martín-Martín, Linxi Fan, Guanzhi Wang, Claudia Pérez-D’Arpino, Shyamal Buch, Sanjana Srivastava, Lyne Tchapmi, et al. iGibson 1.0: a Simulation Environment for Interactive Tasks in Large Realistic Scenes. In *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems*, 2021.
- [65] Mohit Shridhar, Jesse Thomason, Daniel Gordon, Yonatan Bisk, Winson Han, Roozbeh Motlaghi, Luke Zettlemoyer, and Dieter Fox. ALFRED: A Benchmark for Interpreting Grounded Instructions for Everyday Tasks. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2020.
- [66] Andrew Szot, Alexander Clegg, Eric Undersander, Erik Wijmans, Yili Zhao, John Turner, Noah Maestre, Mustafa Mukadam, Devendra Singh Chaplot, Oleksandr Maksymets, et al. Habitat 2.0: Training Home Assistants to Rearrange their Habitat. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 2021.
- [67] Michał Tyszkiewicz, Pascal Fua, and Eduard Trulls. DISK: Learning local features with policy gradient. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 2020.
- [68] Ashish Vaswani, Noam Shazeer, Niki Parmar, Jakob Uszkoreit, Llion Jones, Aidan N Gomez, Łukasz Kaiser, and Illia Polosukhin. Attention is All You Need. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 2017.
- [69] Wenhai Wang, Jifeng Dai, Zhe Chen, Zhenhang Huang, Zhiqi Li, Xizhou Zhu, Xiaowei Hu, Tong Lu, Lewei Lu, Hongsheng Li, et al. InternImage: Exploring Large-Scale Vision Foundation Models With Deformable Convolutions. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2023.
- [70] Saim Wani, Shivansh Patel, Unnat Jain, Angel X. Chang, and Manolis Savva. Multi-ON: Benchmarking Semantic Map Memory using Multi-Object Navigation. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 2020.
- [71] Fei Xia, Amir R Zamir, Zhiyang He, Alexander Sax, Jitendra Malik, and Silvio Savarese. Gibson Env: Real-World Perception for Embodied Agents. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2018.
- [72] Karmesh Yadav, Arjun Majumdar, Ram Ramrakhya, Naoki Yokoyama, Alexei Baevski, Zsolt Kira, Oleksandr Maksymets, and Dhruv Batra. OVRL-V2: A simple state-of-art baseline for ImageNav and ObjectNav. *arXiv:2303.07798*, 2023.
- [73] Karmesh Yadav, Ram Ramrakhya, Arjun Majumdar, Vincent-Pierre Berges, Sachit Kuhar, Dhruv Batra, Alexei Baevski, and Oleksandr Maksymets. Offline Visual Representation Learning for Embodied Navigation. In *Workshop on Reincarnating Reinforcement Learning at ICLR 2023*, 2023.
- [74] Karmesh Yadav, Ram Ramrakhya, Santhosh Kumar Ramakrishnan, Theo Gervet, John Turner, Aaron Gokaslan, Noah Maestre, Angel Xuan Chang, Dhruv Batra, Manolis Savva, et al. Habitat-Matterport 3D Semantics Dataset. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2023.
- [75] Brian Yamauchi. A Frontier-Based Approach for Autonomous Exploration. In *Proceedings of the IEEE International Symposium on Computational Intelligence in Robotics and Automation*, 1997.

- [76] Wei Yang, Xiaolong Wang, Ali Farhadi, Abhinav Gupta, and Roozbeh Mottaghi. Visual Semantic Navigation using Scene Priors. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Learning Representations*, 2019.
- [77] Joel Ye, Dhruv Batra, Abhishek Das, and Erik Wijmans. Auxiliary Tasks and Exploration Enable ObjectNav. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2021.
- [78] Xiaohua Zhai, Xiao Wang, Basil Mustafa, Andreas Steiner, Daniel Keysers, Alexander Kolesnikov, and Lucas Beyer. LiT: Zero-Shot Transfer With Locked-Image Text Tuning. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2022.
- [79] Junyi Zhang, Charles Herrmann, Junhwa Hur, Luisa Polania Cabrera, Varun Jampani, Deqing Sun, and Ming-Hsuan Yang. A Tale of Two Features: Stable Diffusion Complements DINO for Zero-Shot Semantic Correspondence. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 2024.
- [80] Renrui Zhang, Zhengkai Jiang, Ziyu Guo, Shilin Yan, Junting Pan, Hao Dong, Peng Gao, and Hongsheng Li. Personalize Segment Anything Model with One Shot. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Learning Representations*, 2024.
- [81] Minzhao Zhu, Binglei Zhao, and Tao Kong. Navigating to Objects in Unseen Environments by Distance Prediction. In *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems*, 2022.
- [82] Yuke Zhu, Roozbeh Mottaghi, Eric Kolve, Joseph J Lim, Abhinav Gupta, Li Fei-Fei, and Ali Farhadi. Target-driven Visual Navigation in Indoor Scenes using Deep Reinforcement Learning. In *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation*, 2017.

NeurIPS Paper Checklist

1. Claims

Question: Do the main claims made in the abstract and introduction accurately reflect the paper's contributions and scope?

Answer: [Yes]

Justification: Our claims are (i) the introduction of the novel Personalized Instance-based Navigation task, (ii) the build and release of Personalized Instance-based Navigation Embodied Dataset, and (iii) the evaluation of object-driven approaches on this task. Refer to Sec. 3.1 and Sec. 3.2 for tasks definition, to Sec. 3.3 for dataset presentation, to Sec. 4 for the introduction of the baselines and to Sec. 5 for experimental analysis.

Guidelines:

- The answer NA means that the abstract and introduction do not include the claims made in the paper.
- The abstract and/or introduction should clearly state the claims made, including the contributions made in the paper and important assumptions and limitations. A No or NA answer to this question will not be perceived well by the reviewers.
- The claims made should match theoretical and experimental results, and reflect how much the results can be expected to generalize to other settings.
- It is fine to include aspirational goals as motivation as long as it is clear that these goals are not attained by the paper.

2. Limitations

Question: Does the paper discuss the limitations of the work performed by the authors?

Answer: [Yes]

Justification: Limitations of the current dataset and the approaches used to perform the experiments on the task are discussed in the supplemental material.

Guidelines:

- The answer NA means that the paper has no limitation while the answer No means that the paper has limitations, but those are not discussed in the paper.
- The authors are encouraged to create a separate "Limitations" section in their paper.
- The paper should point out any strong assumptions and how robust the results are to violations of these assumptions (e.g., independence assumptions, noiseless settings, model well-specification, asymptotic approximations only holding locally). The authors should reflect on how these assumptions might be violated in practice and what the implications would be.
- The authors should reflect on the scope of the claims made, e.g., if the approach was only tested on a few datasets or with a few runs. In general, empirical results often depend on implicit assumptions, which should be articulated.
- The authors should reflect on the factors that influence the performance of the approach. For example, a facial recognition algorithm may perform poorly when image resolution is low or images are taken in low lighting. Or a speech-to-text system might not be used reliably to provide closed captions for online lectures because it fails to handle technical jargon.
- The authors should discuss the computational efficiency of the proposed algorithms and how they scale with dataset size.
- If applicable, the authors should discuss possible limitations of their approach to address problems of privacy and fairness.
- While the authors might fear that complete honesty about limitations might be used by reviewers as grounds for rejection, a worse outcome might be that reviewers discover limitations that aren't acknowledged in the paper. The authors should use their best judgment and recognize that individual actions in favor of transparency play an important role in developing norms that preserve the integrity of the community. Reviewers will be specifically instructed to not penalize honesty concerning limitations.

3. Theory Assumptions and Proofs

Question: For each theoretical result, does the paper provide the full set of assumptions and a complete (and correct) proof?

Answer: [N/A]

Justification: The paper proposes a dataset and a benchmark for embodied navigation and does not include theory assumptions and proofs.

Guidelines:

- The answer NA means that the paper does not include theoretical results.
- All the theorems, formulas, and proofs in the paper should be numbered and cross-referenced.
- All assumptions should be clearly stated or referenced in the statement of any theorems.
- The proofs can either appear in the main paper or the supplemental material, but if they appear in the supplemental material, the authors are encouraged to provide a short proof sketch to provide intuition.
- Inversely, any informal proof provided in the core of the paper should be complemented by formal proofs provided in appendix or supplemental material.
- Theorems and Lemmas that the proof relies upon should be properly referenced.

4. Experimental Result Reproducibility

Question: Does the paper fully disclose all the information needed to reproduce the main experimental results of the paper to the extent that it affects the main claims and/or conclusions of the paper (regardless of whether the code and data are provided or not)?

Answer: [Yes]

Justification: The codebase along with the dataset is linked in the supplemental material. Moreover, implementation details to reproduce the results are also available in the supplemental material.

Guidelines:

- The answer NA means that the paper does not include experiments.
- If the paper includes experiments, a No answer to this question will not be perceived well by the reviewers: Making the paper reproducible is important, regardless of whether the code and data are provided or not.
- If the contribution is a dataset and/or model, the authors should describe the steps taken to make their results reproducible or verifiable.
- Depending on the contribution, reproducibility can be accomplished in various ways. For example, if the contribution is a novel architecture, describing the architecture fully might suffice, or if the contribution is a specific model and empirical evaluation, it may be necessary to either make it possible for others to replicate the model with the same dataset, or provide access to the model. In general, releasing code and data is often one good way to accomplish this, but reproducibility can also be provided via detailed instructions for how to replicate the results, access to a hosted model (e.g., in the case of a large language model), releasing of a model checkpoint, or other means that are appropriate to the research performed.
- While NeurIPS does not require releasing code, the conference does require all submissions to provide some reasonable avenue for reproducibility, which may depend on the nature of the contribution. For example
 - (a) If the contribution is primarily a new algorithm, the paper should make it clear how to reproduce that algorithm.
 - (b) If the contribution is primarily a new model architecture, the paper should describe the architecture clearly and fully.
 - (c) If the contribution is a new model (e.g., a large language model), then there should either be a way to access this model for reproducing the results or a way to reproduce the model (e.g., with an open-source dataset or instructions for how to construct the dataset).
 - (d) We recognize that reproducibility may be tricky in some cases, in which case authors are welcome to describe the particular way they provide for reproducibility. In the case of closed-source models, it may be that access to the model is limited in

some way (e.g., to registered users), but it should be possible for other researchers to have some path to reproducing or verifying the results.

5. Open access to data and code

Question: Does the paper provide open access to the data and code, with sufficient instructions to faithfully reproduce the main experimental results, as described in supplemental material?

Answer: [Yes]

Justification: The codebase along with the dataset is linked in the supplemental material.

Guidelines:

- The answer NA means that paper does not include experiments requiring code.
- Please see the NeurIPS code and data submission guidelines (<https://nips.cc/public/guides/CodeSubmissionPolicy>) for more details.
- While we encourage the release of code and data, we understand that this might not be possible, so “No” is an acceptable answer. Papers cannot be rejected simply for not including code, unless this is central to the contribution (e.g., for a new open-source benchmark).
- The instructions should contain the exact command and environment needed to run to reproduce the results. See the NeurIPS code and data submission guidelines (<https://nips.cc/public/guides/CodeSubmissionPolicy>) for more details.
- The authors should provide instructions on data access and preparation, including how to access the raw data, preprocessed data, intermediate data, and generated data, etc.
- The authors should provide scripts to reproduce all experimental results for the new proposed method and baselines. If only a subset of experiments are reproducible, they should state which ones are omitted from the script and why.
- At submission time, to preserve anonymity, the authors should release anonymized versions (if applicable).
- Providing as much information as possible in supplemental material (appended to the paper) is recommended, but including URLs to data and code is permitted.

6. Experimental Setting/Details

Question: Does the paper specify all the training and test details (e.g., data splits, hyperparameters, how they were chosen, type of optimizer, etc.) necessary to understand the results?

Answer: [Yes]

Justification: The details in Sec. 4 and Sec. 5 are sufficient to understand the experimental results and the dataset contribution. Additionally, more implementation details are available in the supplemental material.

Guidelines:

- The answer NA means that the paper does not include experiments.
- The experimental setting should be presented in the core of the paper to a level of detail that is necessary to appreciate the results and make sense of them.
- The full details can be provided either with the code, in appendix, or as supplemental material.

7. Experiment Statistical Significance

Question: Does the paper report error bars suitably and correctly defined or other appropriate information about the statistical significance of the experiments?

Answer: [No]

Justification: The main experiments that support the claims of this paper do not require reporting error bars.

Guidelines:

- The answer NA means that the paper does not include experiments.

- The authors should answer "Yes" if the results are accompanied by error bars, confidence intervals, or statistical significance tests, at least for the experiments that support the main claims of the paper.
- The factors of variability that the error bars are capturing should be clearly stated (for example, train/test split, initialization, random drawing of some parameter, or overall run with given experimental conditions).
- The method for calculating the error bars should be explained (closed form formula, call to a library function, bootstrap, etc.)
- The assumptions made should be given (e.g., Normally distributed errors).
- It should be clear whether the error bar is the standard deviation or the standard error of the mean.
- It is OK to report 1-sigma error bars, but one should state it. The authors should preferably report a 2-sigma error bar than state that they have a 96% CI, if the hypothesis of Normality of errors is not verified.
- For asymmetric distributions, the authors should be careful not to show in tables or figures symmetric error bars that would yield results that are out of range (e.g. negative error rates).
- If error bars are reported in tables or plots, The authors should explain in the text how they were calculated and reference the corresponding figures or tables in the text.

8. Experiments Compute Resources

Question: For each experiment, does the paper provide sufficient information on the computer resources (type of compute workers, memory, time of execution) needed to reproduce the experiments?

Answer: [Yes]

Justification: The compute resources used to evaluate the proposed baselines on the task are presented in the supplemental material.

Guidelines:

- The answer NA means that the paper does not include experiments.
- The paper should indicate the type of compute workers CPU or GPU, internal cluster, or cloud provider, including relevant memory and storage.
- The paper should provide the amount of compute required for each of the individual experimental runs as well as estimate the total compute.
- The paper should disclose whether the full research project required more compute than the experiments reported in the paper (e.g., preliminary or failed experiments that didn't make it into the paper).

9. Code Of Ethics

Question: Does the research conducted in the paper conform, in every respect, with the NeurIPS Code of Ethics <https://neurips.cc/public/EthicsGuidelines?>

Answer: [Yes]

Justification: This research is compliant with the NeurIPS Code of Ethics.

Guidelines:

- The answer NA means that the authors have not reviewed the NeurIPS Code of Ethics.
- If the authors answer No, they should explain the special circumstances that require a deviation from the Code of Ethics.
- The authors should make sure to preserve anonymity (e.g., if there is a special consideration due to laws or regulations in their jurisdiction).

10. Broader Impacts

Question: Does the paper discuss both potential positive societal impacts and negative societal impacts of the work performed?

Answer: [Yes]

Justification: The potential societal impacts of ours work are discussed in the supplemental material.

Guidelines:

- The answer NA means that there is no societal impact of the work performed.
- If the authors answer NA or No, they should explain why their work has no societal impact or why the paper does not address societal impact.
- Examples of negative societal impacts include potential malicious or unintended uses (e.g., disinformation, generating fake profiles, surveillance), fairness considerations (e.g., deployment of technologies that could make decisions that unfairly impact specific groups), privacy considerations, and security considerations.
- The conference expects that many papers will be foundational research and not tied to particular applications, let alone deployments. However, if there is a direct path to any negative applications, the authors should point it out. For example, it is legitimate to point out that an improvement in the quality of generative models could be used to generate deepfakes for disinformation. On the other hand, it is not needed to point out that a generic algorithm for optimizing neural networks could enable people to train models that generate Deepfakes faster.
- The authors should consider possible harms that could arise when the technology is being used as intended and functioning correctly, harms that could arise when the technology is being used as intended but gives incorrect results, and harms following from (intentional or unintentional) misuse of the technology.
- If there are negative societal impacts, the authors could also discuss possible mitigation strategies (e.g., gated release of models, providing defenses in addition to attacks, mechanisms for monitoring misuse, mechanisms to monitor how a system learns from feedback over time, improving the efficiency and accessibility of ML).

11. Safeguards

Question: Does the paper describe safeguards that have been put in place for responsible release of data or models that have a high risk for misuse (e.g., pretrained language models, image generators, or scraped datasets)?

Answer: [N/A]

Justification: The release of the codebase and dataset does not present risks of misuse.

Guidelines:

- The answer NA means that the paper poses no such risks.
- Released models that have a high risk for misuse or dual-use should be released with necessary safeguards to allow for controlled use of the model, for example by requiring that users adhere to usage guidelines or restrictions to access the model or implementing safety filters.
- Datasets that have been scraped from the Internet could pose safety risks. The authors should describe how they avoided releasing unsafe images.
- We recognize that providing effective safeguards is challenging, and many papers do not require this, but we encourage authors to take this into account and make a best faith effort.

12. Licenses for existing assets

Question: Are the creators or original owners of assets (e.g., code, data, models), used in the paper, properly credited and are the license and terms of use explicitly mentioned and properly respected?

Answer: [Yes]

Justification: The original owners of the data used in the paper are properly credited, and details on the licenses and terms of use of such data is mentioned in the supplemental material.

Guidelines:

- The answer NA means that the paper does not use existing assets.
- The authors should cite the original paper that produced the code package or dataset.
- The authors should state which version of the asset is used and, if possible, include a URL.

- The name of the license (e.g., CC-BY 4.0) should be included for each asset.
- For scraped data from a particular source (e.g., website), the copyright and terms of service of that source should be provided.
- If assets are released, the license, copyright information, and terms of use in the package should be provided. For popular datasets, paperswithcode.com/datasets has curated licenses for some datasets. Their licensing guide can help determine the license of a dataset.
- For existing datasets that are re-packaged, both the original license and the license of the derived asset (if it has changed) should be provided.
- If this information is not available online, the authors are encouraged to reach out to the asset's creators.

13. **New Assets**

Question: Are new assets introduced in the paper well documented and is the documentation provided alongside the assets?

Answer: [Yes]

Justification: The assets introduced in the paper are described in Sec. 3.3, and further details are included in the supplemental material.

Guidelines:

- The answer NA means that the paper does not release new assets.
- Researchers should communicate the details of the dataset/code/model as part of their submissions via structured templates. This includes details about training, license, limitations, etc.
- The paper should discuss whether and how consent was obtained from people whose asset is used.
- At submission time, remember to anonymize your assets (if applicable). You can either create an anonymized URL or include an anonymized zip file.

14. **Crowdsourcing and Research with Human Subjects**

Question: For crowdsourcing experiments and research with human subjects, does the paper include the full text of instructions given to participants and screenshots, if applicable, as well as details about compensation (if any)?

Answer: [N/A]

Justification: The paper does not involve crowdsourcing nor research with human subjects. The authors of the paper acted as annotators for textually describing the objects selected for the dataset (Sec. 3.3).

Guidelines:

- The answer NA means that the paper does not involve crowdsourcing nor research with human subjects.
- Including this information in the supplemental material is fine, but if the main contribution of the paper involves human subjects, then as much detail as possible should be included in the main paper.
- According to the NeurIPS Code of Ethics, workers involved in data collection, curation, or other labor should be paid at least the minimum wage in the country of the data collector.

15. **Institutional Review Board (IRB) Approvals or Equivalent for Research with Human Subjects**

Question: Does the paper describe potential risks incurred by study participants, whether such risks were disclosed to the subjects, and whether Institutional Review Board (IRB) approvals (or an equivalent approval/review based on the requirements of your country or institution) were obtained?

Answer: [N/A]

Justification: The paper does not involve crowdsourcing nor research with human subjects.

Guidelines:

- The answer NA means that the paper does not involve crowdsourcing nor research with human subjects.
- Depending on the country in which research is conducted, IRB approval (or equivalent) may be required for any human subjects research. If you obtained IRB approval, you should clearly state this in the paper.
- We recognize that the procedures for this may vary significantly between institutions and locations, and we expect authors to adhere to the NeurIPS Code of Ethics and the guidelines for their institution.
- For initial submissions, do not include any information that would break anonymity (if applicable), such as the institution conducting the review.